

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF PREOPERATIVE PREPARATION IN CHILDREN WITH WIDESPREAD APPENDICULAR PERITONITIS

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Abstract: The aim of the study is to develop comprehensive preoperative preparation for children with diffuse appendicular peritonitis (DAP). During 2015-2016, 63 children with DAP were under our observation. In the reactive phase of the disease were 11 (17.4%) patients, in the toxic phase - 42 (66.6%), and in the terminal phase - 10 (16%). Among the hospitalized children, 7 (11.1%) were under 3 years of age, 12 (19%) were aged 4 to 7 years, 23 (36.5%) were aged 8 to 12 years, and 21 (33.3%) were aged 13 to 18 years. Preoperative preparation included all therapeutic measures aimed at normalizing the vital functions of the body, and these were implemented sequentially according to their vital significance. Several factors were taken into account when determining the volume of preoperative infusion: basic (physiological) needs, preoperative fluid deficit, losses into the third space, and transcellular fluid losses. The developed intensive therapy method enabled positive stabilization of homeostasis indicators, reduction of intoxication, optimization of impaired vital bodily functions, and contributed to a favorable course of anesthesia and surgery.

Key words: enzymatic peritonitis, pancreonecrosis, laparoscopy, baby

Introduction

Despite significant progress in modern pediatric surgery, widespread appendicular peritonitis (WAP) remains a serious purulent-septic disease that is the main cause of sepsis and multiple organ failure syndrome development in children.

Despite the existence of numerous treatment methods for widespread appendicular peritonitis, postoperative complications in children occur in 10-15% of cases, while the mortality rate remains high (up to 20-30%). In recent years, there has been a decrease in mortality during the early stages of the disease. However, the mortality rate remains high (30-50%) in cases where patients are admitted in advanced stages with diseases accompanied by the development of paralytic intestinal obstruction (PIO).

Treatment of TAP in children presents significant challenges and consists of three main stages: preoperative preparation, surgical intervention, and postoperative period.

Considering that children with diffuse appendicular peritonitis experience severe disruptions in homeostasis, immediate surgical intervention is considered a serious mistake, as these changes can worsen during and after surgery. Therefore, preoperative preparation should encompass all treatment methods

aimed at normalizing the body's vital functions and ensure the appropriate sequence of medical procedures based on the activity level of vital organs.

This article presents our personal experience in conducting comprehensive intensive care during the preoperative period in children with diffuse appendicular peritonitis (DAP).

Research materials and methods.

During 2015-2016, 63 children with generalized forms of appendicular peritonitis underwent surgery at the Children's Surgical Clinic of Samarkand State Medical University. Of these, 38 (60.3%) were boys and 25 (39.7%) were girls. All cases of TAP were caused by destructive forms of appendicitis, and in most cases, the cause of diffuse peritonitis was perforation of the appendix, which accounted for 82.6% of cases of diffuse appendicular peritonitis. The diffuse form of TAP was detected in 37 (58.7%) patients, while the generalized form was found in 26 (41.3%) patients. At the reactive stage of the disease, 11 (17.4%) patients were hospitalized, at the toxic stage - 42 (66.6%), and at the terminal stage - 10 (16%). The age distribution of patients was as follows: up to 3 years old - 7 (11.1%), from 4 to 7 years old - 12 (19%), from 8 to 12 years old - 23 (36.5%), from 13 to 18 years old - 21 (21.6%) patients. All patients underwent standard clinical examinations: complete blood count and urinalysis, blood type determination, coagulation profile, biochemical blood tests, ECG, chest and abdominal X-rays as indicated, immunological and microbiological studies, as well as abdominal ultrasound diagnostics.

Research results and their discussion

Following initial examination, clinical and laboratory studies, ultrasound monitoring, and diagnosis, all children with complicated forms of acute appendicitis were admitted to the intensive care unit. There, preoperative treatment was conducted for 8-12 hours in the following sequence: aspiration of gastric contents through a nasogastric tube, administration of cleansing enema, inhalation of humidified and heated oxygen, infusion therapy aimed at restoring adequate fluid volume in blood vessels, measures to stabilize acid-base and electrolyte balance, improve the body's oxygen supply, and normalize the state of the blood coagulation system.

The fundamental importance of this approach lies in the fact that children have more difficulty compensating for hypovolemia than adults (which occurs through increased stroke volume and increased heart rate). Consequently, children face a higher risk of compensated hypovolemic shock progressing to decompensated and potentially irreversible shock. Another crucial aspect that prompted us to fundamentally reconsider the volume and nature of preoperative infusion therapy in children is that their glucose metabolism is 3-4 times faster than in adults. As a result, even short-term hypoglycemia can lead to irreversible changes in the brain.

The main objective of infusion therapy is to eliminate the initial fluid deficit, meet physiological needs, and compensate for pathological losses. Fluid loss was calculated by measuring the volume of urine, feces, vomit, and discharge from the gastric tube. To the volume of fluid loss determined in this way, an additional 45% was added to account for sweating (15%) and evaporation from the body surface (30%).

All patients underwent catheterization of central veins (in the elbow area), and in some cases, the subclavian veins.

When calculating the volume of preoperative infusion, several factors were taken into consideration: basic (physiological) needs, preoperative fluid deficit, and third-space fluid losses.

Basic (physiological) fluid requirements were calculated as follows:

- For body weight less than 10 kg: 100 ml/kg;
- For body weight from 11 kg to 20 kg: 1 l + 50 ml for each kilogram over 10 kg;

- For body weight over 20 kg: 1.5 l + 20 ml for each kilogram over 20 kg.

Considering that our time for preoperative preparation was limited (8-12 hours), the hourly calculation of the physiological fluid requirement was carried out as follows:

- For body weight less than 10 kg: 4 ml/kg/hour;
- For body weight from 11 to 20 kg: 40 ml/hour + 2 ml/hour for each kilogram over 10 kg;
- For body weight more than 20 kg: 60 ml/hour + 1 ml/hour for each kilogram over 20 kg.

The data used as the basis for calculating preoperative fluid deficit replenishment were: medical history, physical examination, assessment of key hemodynamic indicators (heart rate, arterial blood pressure, central venous pressure), monitoring of diuresis (where urine output less than 0.5 ml/kg/hour is considered a sign of dehydration or inadequate hemodynamics), results of laboratory blood tests (hemoglobin, hematocrit, electrolytes, urea, creatinine), specific gravity and concentration of sodium in urine.

Oxygen therapy was conducted under constant clinical and laboratory monitoring:

Humidified heated oxygen was administered at a volume of 2-5 l/min for 20-30 minutes with a 30-minute interval.

In hypovolemic shock, hemodynamic disturbances were corrected using a mixture of crystalloid and colloid solutions in a 50:50 ratio. During the first hour, the preparations were administered intravenously at a volume of 20-30 ml/kg. Then infusion therapy was continued at a volume of 10 ml/kg/hour until diuresis was restored.

Hypovolemia and dehydration were addressed according to the phase of TAP. Specifically, in the reactive phase, only 0.9% isotonic sodium chloride solution at a rate of 15-20 ml/kg/hour; Succinasol and 5% glucose solution were administered at a rate of 10-15 ml/kg/hour. In the toxic phase, in addition to these preparations, rheopolyglucin 15-20 ml/kg; glucose solution with 10% insulin, Ringer's solution - 12-15 ml/kg, and polyglucin - 10-20 ml/kg were added.

Biochemical parameters were corrected as follows: Succinasol and 5% glucose solution were administered at a rate of 10-15 ml/kg/hour. In the toxic phase, these drugs are supplemented with rheopolyglucin 15-20 ml/kg;

- in the reactive phase, intravenously in a 5-10% glucose solution (slowly), 7.5% potassium chloride solution up to 3 mmol/kg/day; 10% sodium chloride solution at a dose of 1-2 to 3-5 mmol/kg/day, depending on age, at 12-15 drops/minute;
- in the toxic phase, a 4% sodium bicarbonate solution was added dropwise to the above solutions at a dose of 1-2 mmol/kg;
- in the toxic phase, a 4% sodium bicarbonate solution was added dropwise to the above solutions at a dose of 1-2 mmol/kg;
- In the stage of polymorphic disorders, potassium-magnesium aspartate (PMA) was added at a rate of 7-10 ml/kg; additionally, a 10% NaCl solution and a 4% sodium bicarbonate solution were administered at the aforementioned doses, as well as rheopolyglucin and polyglucin at rates of 8-12 and 7-10 ml/kg, respectively.

Surgical intervention for diffuse peritonitis is always performed under multicomponent general anesthesia and artificial lung ventilation. 7-10 ml/kg;

Surgical intervention for diffuse peritonitis is always performed under multicomponent general anesthesia and artificial lung ventilation.

Antibacterial therapy was carried out by intravenous administration of broad-spectrum antibiotics 30-40 minutes before the start of the operation.

Due to the inevitable mechanical disruption of biological barriers that limit the area of the infectious process and the natural intestinal biocenosis during surgical intervention, we believe that surgical intervention in TAP should be performed after achieving therapeutic concentrations of antibacterial drugs in the blood and tissues.

Preparation for surgical intervention in children with TAP, which begins immediately after diagnosis, concludes in the operating room and gradually transitions to anesthetic management of the operation. All patients underwent complete intravenous anesthesia with ketamine after premedication in the reactive phase of peritonitis, with intravenous administration of droperidol (0.25-0.3 mg/kg), fentanyl (0.008-0.015 mg/kg) or sodium oxybutyrate (GABA) - 80-120 mg/kg in the toxic phase and in the phase of polymorphic disorders.

Anesthesia was administered using the endotracheal method with muscle relaxants and continuous oxygen inhalation at 3-5 l/min. The intensive therapy, which began in the preoperative period, was continued during anesthesia and surgery. The aforementioned complex intensive preoperative treatment method applied to children with RAP significantly reduced intoxication, maximally improved homeostasis indicators, and effectively corrected disorders of the body's vital functions. This facilitated a smooth course of anesthesia and positively influenced the postoperative period.

Conclusions.

1. Preoperative preparation of children with diffuse appendicular peritonitis should include all necessary individualized corrective therapy aimed at normalizing vital bodily functions.
2. Targeted infusion therapy, corresponding to each stage of diffuse appendicular peritonitis, allows for optimal correction of homeostasis indicators and disorders of vital bodily functions.
3. Implementing the developed complex of intensive preoperative therapy in children with diffuse appendicular peritonitis also contributed to a favorable course of anesthesia and postoperative period.

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